

On quadratic Diophantine Equations

$$x^2 - (t^2 - t)y^2 - ((2p)^2t - 2p)x + ((2p)^2t^2 - (2p)^2t)y = 0$$

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Abstract

Let $t \geq 2$ be a positive integer and $p \geq 1$ be any fixed integer. Extending the work of A. Tekcan, here we consider the number of integer solutions of Diophantine equation $E : x^2 - (t^2 - t)y^2 - ((2p)^2t - 2p)x + ((2p)^2t^2 - (2p)^2t)y = 0$. We also obtain some formulas and recurrence relations on the integer solution (x_n, y_n) of E . Equally, we are able to solve the equation $\tilde{E} : u^2 - (t^2 - t)v^2 = p^2 + 4t(p^4 - p^3)$ which is a simple transformation of E via an appropriate transformation T .

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1 Introduction

A Diophantine equation is an algebraic equation whose coefficients lie in the ring \mathbb{Z} of rational integers and whose solutions are sought in that ring. The name comes from Diophantus, an Alexandrian mathematician of the third century A.D., who proposed many Diophantine problems ; but such equations have a very long history, extending back to ancient Egypt, Babylonia, and Greece. In general, the Diophantine equation is an equation given by

$$ax^2 + bxy + cy^2 + dx + ey + f = 0.$$

The equation

$$x^2 - dy^2 = 1$$

is a special case of Diophantine equation, known as the Pell equation.

Pell's equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = 1$ was solved by Lagrange in terms of simple continued fractions. Lagrange was the first to prove that $x^2 - Dy^2 = 1$ has infinitely many solutions in integers if $D \neq 1$ is a fixed positive non-square

integer. If the length of the period of \sqrt{D} is l , all positive solutions are given by $x = P_{2vk-1}$ and $y = Q_{2vk-1}$ if k is odd, and by $x = P_{vk-1}$ and $y = Q_{vk-1}$ if k is even, where $v = 1, 2, \dots$ and $\frac{P_n}{Q_n}$ denotes the n th convergent of the continued fraction expansion of \sqrt{D} . Incidentally, $x = P_{(2v-1)(k-1)}$ and $y = Q_{(2v-1)(k-1)}$, $v = 1, 2, \dots$, are the positive solutions of $x^2 - Dy^2 = -1$ provided that l is odd.

There is no solution of $x^2 - Dy^2 = \pm 1$ other than $x_v, y_v : v = 1, 2, \dots$ given by $(x_1 + \sqrt{D}y_1)^v = x_v + \sqrt{D}y_v$, where x_1, y_1 is the least positive solution called the fundamental solution, which there are different methods for finding it. The reader can find many references in the subject in the book [9].

For completeness we recall that there are many papers in which are considered different types of Pell's equation. Many authors such as Tekcan [3], Kaplan and Williams [4], Matthews [5], Mollin, Poorten and Williams [6], Steinhagen [7] and the others consider some specific Pell equations and their integer solutions. A. Tekcan in [3], considered the equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = \pm 4$, and he obtained some formulas for its integer solutions. He mentioned two conjectures which were proved by A. S. Shabani [8]. In [1], we considered the Pell equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = \pm k^2$ when $D \neq 1$ be a positive non-square and $k \geq 2$, we obtain some formulas for its integer solutions.

2 The Diophantine Equation $x^2 - (t^2 - t)y^2 - ((2p)^2t - 2p)x + ((2p)^2t^2 - (2p)^2t)y = 0$

Let $t \geq 2$ be an integer. In [2], A. Tekcan considered the number of integer solutions of Diophantine equation $D : x^2 - (t^2 - t)y^2 - (4t - 2)x + (4t^2 - 4t)y = 0$ over \mathbb{Z} . He also derived some recurrence relations on the integer solutions (x_n, y_n) of D . In the present paper, we consider the integer solutions of Diophantine equation

$$E : x^2 - (t^2 - t)y^2 - ((2p)^2t - 2p)x + ((2p)^2t^2 - (2p)^2t)y = 0 \quad (1)$$

over \mathbb{Z} , where $t \geq 2$ and $p \geq 1$ be two integers.

Note that the resolution of E in its present form is very difficult, that is, we can not determine how many solutions E has and what they are. So, we have to transform E into an appropriate Diophantine equation which can be easily solved. To get this let

$$T : \begin{cases} x = u + h \\ y = v + k \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

be a translation for some h and k .

By applying the transformation T to E , we get

$$T(E) := \tilde{E} : \begin{aligned} & (u+h)^2 - (t^2-t)(v+k)^2 - ((2p)^2t - 2p)(u+h) \\ & + ((2p)^2t^2 - (2p)^2t)(v+k) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In (3), we obtain $u(2h+2p-(2p)^2t)$ and $v(-2kt^2+2kt+(2p)^2t^2-(2p)^2t)$. So we get $h = 2p^2t - p$ and $k = 2p^2$. Consequently for $x = u + 2p^2t - p$ and $y = v + 2p^2$, we have the Diophantine equation

$$\tilde{E} : u^2 - (t^2 - t)v^2 = p^2 + 4t(p^4 - p^3) \quad (4)$$

which is a Pell equation.

It is clear that D , considered in [2], is a particular case of E ($p = 1$).

Now, we try to find all integer solutions (u_n, v_n) of $T(E)$ and then we can retransfer all results from $T(E)$ to E by using the inverse of T .

Theorem 2.1 *Let \tilde{E} be the Diophantine equation in (3), then*

(1) *The fundamental solution of \tilde{E} is $(u_1, v_1) = (2p^2t - p, 2p^2)$.*

(2) *Define the sequence (u_n, v_n) by*

$$\begin{cases} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2p^2t - p \\ 2p^2 \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} u_n \\ v_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2t-1 & 2t^2-2t \\ 2 & 2t-1 \end{pmatrix}^{n-1} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \end{pmatrix}, \forall n \geq 2. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Then (u_n, v_n) is a solution of \tilde{E} .

(3) *The solutions (u_n, v_n) satisfy the recurrence relations*

$$\begin{cases} u_n = (2t-1)u_{n-1} + (2t^2-2t)v_{n-1} \\ v_n = 2u_{n-1} + (2t-1)v_{n-1} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

for $n \geq 2$

(4) *The solutions (u_n, v_n)*

$$\begin{cases} u_n = (4t-3)(u_{n-1} + u_{n-2}) - u_{n-3} \\ v_n = (4t-3)(v_{n-1} + v_{n-2}) - v_{n-3} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

for $n \geq 4$

(5) The n -th solution (u_n, v_n) can be given by

$$\frac{u_n}{v_n} = \left[t - 1; \underbrace{2, 2t - 2, \dots, 2, 2t - 2}_{n-1 \text{ times}}, 1, 2p - 1 \right], \forall n \geq 1. \quad (8)$$

Proof.

(1) It is easily seen that $(u_1, v_1) = (2p^2t - p, 2p^2)$ is the fundamental solution of \tilde{E} , since $(2p^2t - p)^2 - (t^2 - t)(2p^2)^2 = p^2 + 4t(p^4 - p^3)$.

(2) We prove it using the method of mathematical induction. Let $n = 1$, by (5) we get $(u_1, v_1) = (2p^2t - p, 2p^2)$ which is the fundamental solution and so is a solution of \tilde{E} . Now, we assume that the Diophantine equation (4) is satisfied for n , that is $\tilde{E} : u_n^2 - (t^2 - t)v_n^2 = p^2 + 4t(p^4 - p^3)$. We try to show that this equation is also satisfied for $n + 1$. Applying (5), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} u_{n+1} \\ v_{n+1} \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} 2t - 1 & 2t^2 - 2t \\ 2 & 2t - 1 \end{pmatrix}^n \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} 2t - 1 & 2t^2 - 2t \\ 2 & 2t - 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2t - 1 & 2t^2 - 2t \\ 2 & 2t - 1 \end{pmatrix}^{n-1} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} 2t - 1 & 2t^2 - 2t \\ 2 & 2t - 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u_n \\ v_n \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} (2t - 1)u_n + (2t^2 - 2t)v_n \\ 2u_n + (2t - 1)v_n \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Hence, we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} u_{n+1}^2 - (t^2 - t)v_{n+1}^2 &= [(2t - 1)u_n + (2t^2 - 2t)v_n]^2 - (t^2 - t)[2u_n + (2t - 1)v_n]^2 \\ &= u_n^2 - (t^2 - t)v_n^2 = p^2 + 4t(p^4 - p^3). \end{aligned}$$

So (u_{n+1}, v_{n+1}) is also solution of \tilde{E} .

(3) Using (9), we find that

$$\begin{cases} u_n = (2t - 1)u_{n-1} + (2t^2 - 2t)v_{n-1} \\ v_n = 2u_{n-1} + (2t - 1)v_{n-1} \end{cases}$$

for $n \geq 2$

(4) We prove it using the method of mathematical induction. For $n = 4$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} u_1 &= 2p^2t - p \\ u_2 &= 8p^2t^2 - 2(3p^2 + p)t + p \\ u_3 &= 32p^2t^2 - 8(5p^2 + p)t^2 + 2(5p^2 + 4p^2)t - p \end{aligned}$$

and

$$u_4 = 128p^2t^4 - 32(7p^2 + p)t^3 + 16(7p^2 + 3p)t^2 - 2(7p^2 + 9p)t + p. \text{ Hence}$$

$$\begin{aligned} u_4 &= 128p^2t^4 - 32(7p^2 + p)t^3 + 16(7p^2 + 3p)t^2 - 2(7p^2 + 9p)t + p. \\ &= (4t - 3)[32p^2t^3 - (32p^2 + 8p)t^2 + (4p^2 + 6p)t] - (2p^2t - p) \\ &= (4t - 3)[32p^2t^2 - 8(5p^2 + p)t^2 + 2(5p^2 + 4p^2)t - p + 8p^2t^2 - 2(3p^2 + p)t \\ &\quad + p] - (2p^2t - p) \\ &= (4t - 3)(u_3 + u_2) - u_1. \end{aligned}$$

So $u_n = (4t - 3)(u_{n-1} + u_{n-2}) - u_{n-3}$. is satisfied for $n = 4$. Let us assume that this relation is satisfied for n , that is,

$$u_n = (4t - 3)(u_{n-1} + u_{n-2}) - u_{n-3}. \quad (10)$$

Then using (9) and (10), we conclude that

$$u_{n+1} = (4t - 3)(u_n + u_{n-1}) - u_{n-2},$$

completing the proof.

Similarly, we prove that $v_n = (4t - 3)(v_{n-1} + v_{n-2}) - v_{n-3}$, $\forall n \geq 4$.

(5) We prove it using the method of mathematical induction. For $n = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{u_1}{v_1} &= \frac{2p^2t - p}{2p^2} = t - 1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2p - 1}} \\ &= [t - 1; 1, 2p - 1] \end{aligned}$$

which is the fundamental solution of \tilde{E} . Let us assume that the n -th solution (u_n, v_n) is given by

$$\frac{u_n}{v_n} = \left[t - 1; \underbrace{2, 2t - 2, \dots, 2, 2t - 2}_{n-1 \text{ times}}, 1, 2p - 1 \right].$$

and we show that it holds for (u_{n+1}, y_{n+1}) .

Using (6) , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{u_{n+1}}{v_{n+1}} &= \frac{(2t-1)u_n + (2t^2-2t)v_n}{2u_n + (2t-1)v_n} \\
 &= \frac{2(t-1)u_n + u_n + (2t-1)(t-1)v_n + (t-1)v_n}{2u_n + (2t-1)v_n} \\
 &= t-1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{t-1 + \frac{u_n}{v_n}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

as

$$\begin{aligned}
 t-1 + \frac{u_n}{v_n} &= t-1 + t-1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{\dots + \frac{1}{2t-2 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2p-1}}}}} \\
 &= 2t-2 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{2t-2 + \frac{1}{\dots + \frac{1}{2t-2 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2p-1}}}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{u_{n+1}}{v_{n+1}} &= t-1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{2t-2 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{2t-2 + \frac{1}{\dots + \frac{1}{2t-2 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2p-1}}}}}}} \\
 &= \left[t-1; \underbrace{2, 2t-2, \dots, 2, 2t-2}_{n \text{ times}}, 1, 2p-1 \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

completing the proof.

As we reported above, the Diophantine equation E could be transformed into the Diophantine equation \tilde{E} via the transformation T . Also, we showed that $x = u + 2p^2t - p$ and $y = v + 2p^2$. So, we can retransfer all results from \tilde{E} to E by applying the inverse of T . Thus, we can give the following main theorem

Theorem 2.2 *Let D be the Diophantine equation in (1). Then*

(1) *The fundamental (minimal) solution of E is $(x_1, y_1) = (4p^2t - 2p, 4p^2)$*

(2) *Define the sequence $\{(x_n, y_n)\}_{n \geq 1} = \{(u_n + 2p^2t - p, v_n + 2p^2)\}$, where $\{(x_n, y_n)\}$ defined in (5). Then (x_n, y_n) is a solution of E . So it has infinitely many integer solutions $(x_n, y_n) \in \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$.*

(3) *The solutions (x_n, y_n) satisfy the recurrence relations*

$$\begin{cases} x_n = (2t - 1)x_{n-1} + (2t^2 - 2t)y_{n-1} - 8p^2t^2 + (8p^2 + 2p)t - 2p \\ y_n = 2x_{n-1} + (2t - 1)y_{n-1} - 8p^2t + 4p^2 + 2p \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

for $n \geq 2$

(4) *The solutions (u_n, v_n) satisfy the recurrence relations*

$$\begin{cases} x_n = (4t - 3)(x_{n-1} + x_{n-2}) - x_{n-3} - 16p^2t^2 + (16p^2 + 8p)t - 8p \\ y_n = (4t - 3)(y_{n-1} + y_{n-2}) - y_{n-3} - 16p^2t + 16p^2. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

for $n \geq 4$

Example 2.3 *Let $t = 4$ and $p = 2$. Then $(u_1, v_1) = (30, 8)$ is the fundamental solution of*

$$\tilde{E} : u^2 - 12v^2 = 132$$

and some other solutions are

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_2 \\ v_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 7 & 24 \\ 2 & 7 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 30 \\ 8 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 402 \\ 116 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_3 \\ v_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 7 & 24 \\ 2 & 7 \end{pmatrix}^2 \begin{pmatrix} 30 \\ 8 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 5598 \\ 1616 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_4 \\ v_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 7 & 24 \\ 2 & 7 \end{pmatrix}^3 \begin{pmatrix} 30 \\ 8 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 77970 \\ 22508 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_5 \\ v_5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 7 & 24 \\ 2 & 7 \end{pmatrix}^4 \begin{pmatrix} 30 \\ 8 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1085982 \\ 313496 \end{pmatrix}$$

Further

$$\frac{u_1}{v_1} = [3; , 1, 3] = \frac{30}{8}$$

$$\frac{u_2}{v_2} = [3; 2, 6, 1, 3] = \frac{402}{116}$$

$$\frac{u_3}{v_3} = [3; 2, 6, 2, 6, 1, 3] = \frac{5598}{1616}$$

$$\frac{u_4}{v_4} = [3; 2, 6, 2, 6, 2, 6, 1, 3] = \frac{77970}{22508}$$

$$\frac{u_5}{v_5} = [3; 2, 6, 2, 6, 2, 6, 2, 6, 1, 3] = \frac{1085982}{313496}$$

It can be concluded now, that the fundamental solution of

$$E : x^2 - 12y^2 - 60x + 192y = 0$$

is (60, 16). Some other solutions are

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_2 \\ y_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 432 \\ 124 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_3 \\ y_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 5628 \\ 1624 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_4 \\ y_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 78000 \\ 22516 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_5 \\ y_5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1086012 \\ 313504 \end{pmatrix}$$

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